

Analysis of College Students’ Attitude towards Online Shopping in Nagercoil, Kanniyakumari District

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Abstract

Online shopping has been a growing trend in all four corners of the world, especially among the countries possessing highly developed infrastructure available for marketing performance through the internet. Internet marketing is conceptually different from other marketing channels and internet promotes a one to one communication between the seller and the end user with round the clock customer service. Analysing consumer attitude is the main part in the success of any business. To ensure the success of the online business, it is important for the online marketers to understand their targeted customers. The current study focuses on the attitude of college students towards online shopping with special reference to Nagercoil, Kanniyakumari District. First-hand data was collected from 120 sample college students of different socio-economic strata by adopting Judgement sampling technique with structured interview schedule. Appropriate statistical tools like frequency analysis, factor analysis were used to analyze the collected data and arrive at the result. Analysis of the collected data revealed that Comfortable was the most important factor and the significant variable was shopping convenience. Recommendations for improvement in shopping convenience to enhance their influence have also been made.

Keyword: College Students, Attitude, Online Shopping.

Introduction

The world of the internet practically can be considered as an endless market, where a consumer living in any country in the world can buy goods from any web trader operating anywhere in the world. Items which are not available in the surroundings of the consumer can also be purchased as the choice of goods is significantly wider. Today the amount of trade that is conducted electronically using e-commerce has increased with a wide spread usage of internet and technology and online shopping is going to be the future shopping in the world.

According to Internet World Status, India has the third largest number of internet users in the world after China, and the USA despite having a low internet penetration of just 8.5 percent. India’s count of internet users has also been increasing at a CAGR of 35 percent from 2007(Nirmala and Harisevitha, 2015). As per the Internet and Mobile Association of India and IMRB 2017 report Rural India is

increasingly becoming an important part of internet growth. There were an estimated 269 million urban internet users in December 2016, while in rural India, there were 163 million internet users. According to Boston Consulting Group 2017 report from 2014 through 2016, the number of online buyers rose seven-fold, to between 80 million and 90 million. By 2020, half of all internet users will be rural and also, 40 percent of users will be women. India is also expected to have more than 850 million online users by 2025. Digitally influenced spending, currently USD 45-50 billion a year, is projected to increase more than ten-fold, to between USD 500-550 billion and to account for 30-35 percent of all retail sales by 2025.

Statement of Problem

Online shopping has been a growing trend in all four corners of the world, especially among the countries possessing highly developed infrastructure available for marketing performance through the internet. Most of the companies are running their online portals to sell their products and services. Internet marketing is conceptually different from other marketing channels and internet promotes a one to one communication between the seller and the end user with round the clock customer service. Consumers have different personalities, which may influence their shopping behavior. Analysing consumer attitude is the main part in the success of any business. To ensure the success of the online business, it is important for the online marketers to understand their targeted customers. Hence this study has attempted to analyze the attitude of college students towards online shopping with special reference to Nagercoil, Kanniyakumari District.

Objectives

- To study the demographic profile of sample college students in Nagercoil.
- To examine the sample respondents' online buying behavior.
- To analyze sample college students' attitude towards online shopping in the study area.

Methodology

In this study, a sample size of 120 sample college students of different socio-economic strata was chosen by adopting Judgement sampling technique for gathering first-hand data with the help of a structured interview schedule. The secondary data were collected from journals, books and websites. The collected data were analyzed, summarized and interpreted with the help of appropriate statistical tools like Simple Percentage and Factor Analysis. The scope of the present study is limited to Nagercoil, Kanniyakumari District.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Sample Respondents

Age	Age	No. of respondents	Percentage
	18-20	61	50.8
	21-23	47	39.2
	Above 23	12	10.0
	Total	120	100
Gender	Gender	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Male	34	28.3
	Female	86	71.7
		Total	120

Marital Status	Status	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Unmarried	109	90.8
	Married	11	09.2
	Total	120	100
Educational Qualification	Educaion Qualification	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Under Graduate	57	47.5
	Post Graduate	48	40.0
	Professional	15	12.5
	Total	120	100
Area of Residence	Area	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Urban	58	48.3
	Rural	62	51.7
	Total	120	100
Monthly Income of the Family	Income	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Up to Rs.20000	28	23.3
	Rs.20000 -30000	45	37.5
	Rs.30000-40000	21	17.5
	Rs.40000-50000	15	12.5
	Above Rs.50000	11	09.2
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary data

Table 1 shows that 50.8 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 18-20years; 71.7 percent of the respondents are female; among the total respondents 90.8 percent are unmarried; 47.5 percent are under graduates; 51.7 percent of the respondents live in rural area and 37.5 percent of the respondents belong to the family income group of Rs.20000-30000.

Table 2 Buying Behaviour of the Sample Respondents

Frequency of Online Shopping	Frequency	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Once in a month	61	50.8
	Once in 3 months	47	39.2
	Once in 6 months	12	10.0
	Once in a year	05	04.2
	Total	120	100
Sources of Idea about Online Shopping	Sources	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Friends	57	47.5
	Advertisement	35	29.2
	Search Engine	28	23.3
	Total	120	100

Mode of Online Shopping	Online Shopping	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Websites	52	43.3
	Mobile Apps	68	56.7
	Total	120	100

Mode of Payment	Mode	No. of respondents	Percentage
	Cash on Delivery	74	61.7
	Debit/Credit Card	31	25.8
	Net Banking	15	12.5
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 shows that 48.3 percent of the respondents are shopping monthly; 47.5 per cent of the respondents gather information about online shopping from their friends; 56.7 percent of the respondents use mobile phone applications for their online shopping and 61.7 percent of the respondents have chosen cash on delivery as their mode of payment.

Factor Analysis of College Students' Attitude towards Online Shopping

The data regarding the attitudes influencing the sample college students' online shopping behavior were collected from them for Factor analysis which was applied to find out the prime influencing factor. The inter-correlations between 19 variables were analyzed using Principal Component Analysis and Varimax Rotation and the results were exhibited in Table 3. Before applying the data for factor analysis, sampling adequacy was tested by KMO and Bartlett's Test which revealed that the value of KMO (0.702) was greater than 0.5 and hence the sample was adequate.

Table 3 Rotated Component Matrix of College Students' Attitude towards Online Shopping

Factor	Variable	Components				
		1	2	3	4	5
Comfortable	Shopping Convenience	.874	-.203	-.038	.122	.119
	More Relaxed Shopping	.748	.170	.050	.035	.008
	Shopping at any time, from anywhere	.671	.087	.098	-.252	-.113
	No Need to Travel to Shop	.583	-.182	.111	-.009	.189
	More Easier Shopping	.563	-.206	.096	.020	-.305
Product	Wide Variety of Products	.164	.852	.162	.028	.045
	Detailed Description about the Products	-.138	.740	.061	.190	.021
	Access of Global Level Brand	.047	.653	.189	.015	-.052
	Product Ratings	-.046	.571	-.480	.171	.116
	Customer Review about Products	.106	.528	-.487	.174	.114

Price	Low Price	.223	.080	.770	.107	-.011
	Comparison of Prices of Different Suppliers	.130	.097	.689	-.086	-.134
	Different Mode of payment	-.080	.386	.585	.388	-.139
Sales Promotion	Offer/Discount	.030	.273	-.199	.758	.450
	Easy Mode of Return	.305	-.083	.041	.681	-.018
	Customer Service	-.040	.253	.008	.568	-.011
	Advertisement	-.041	.253	.008	.506	-.011
Psychological	Hedonic	.039	-.054	-.093	.001	.746
	Having Fun	.324	-.025	.081	.077	.679

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

The factor analysis narrates the 19 variables into five important factors namely Comfortable, Product, Price, Sales Promotion and Psychological. All these five factors explain that the attitudes influence the sample college students in online shopping to the extent of 62.741 percent.

The most important factor is Comfortable which consists of five variables (significant – Shopping Convenience) with the Eigen value of 3.841 and Percentage of variance is 22.432. The second important factor is Product which consists of five variables (significant-Wide Variety of Products) with the Eigen value of 2.746 and Percentage of variance 17.192. The third important factor is Price with – three variables (significant –Low Price), Eigen value of 1.661 and Percentage of variance 9.631 which is followed by sales Promotion with -four variables (significant –Offer/Discount), Eigen value 1.402 and Percentage of variance 7.215 and Psychological with - two variables (significant-Hedonic), Eigen value of 1.084 and Percentage of variance 6.271.

Findings

- 50.8 percent of the respondents are in the age group of 18-20 years and 71.7 percent of the respondents are female.
- 90.8 percent of the respondents are unmarried, and 47.5 percent are under graduates.
- 51.7per cent of the respondents are living in rural areas and 37.5 percent of the respondents belong to the family income group of Rs.20000-30000.
- 48.3 percent of the respondents are shopping monthly and 47.5 percent of the respondents gather information about online shopping from their friends.
- 56.7 percent of the respondents use mobile phone applications for their online shopping.
- 61.7 percent of the respondents have chosen cash on delivery as their mode of payment.
- Factor analysis which is applied to find out the influence of Sample College students' attitude towards online shopping narrates the 19 variables into five important factors.
- All these five factors explain that the 19variables are considered to the extent of 62.741 percent.
- Among the five factors, the most important is Comfortable which is followed by Product and Price.

Suggestions

- Online marketers should concentrate, to a remarkable extent, in the area of better quality products and friendly after-sale services.

- Additional services should be provided to the consumers to woo them and build upon loyalty.
- Fair and competitive price for the products should be provided to attract online shoppers.
- Online marketers should use innovative sales promotion strategies to attract online shoppers.

Conclusion

Online shopping is a borderless entity that helps the consumers to shop comfortably. Online shopping is becoming increasingly popular and the advent of technology in the recent period being the primary reason for it. Today's is a consumer market and as a result, the priority is the consumer satisfaction. Hence online marketers have to understand their targeted customers and change their attitude towards the market to retain their customers thereby ensure a stable sales in the years to come.

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